

KNOWLEDGE OF OTALGIA (EARACHE) AMONGST THE POPULATION OF LAHORE

Syed Ahmed Shahzaem Hussain,¹ Syed Ahmed Shahzain Hussain,² Syed Muzahir Hussain³

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Abstract

Background: Otolgia or ear pain is a unique symptom with a vast array of possible causes, complex clinical presentations and a broad spectrum of severity. Despite this, as with any common symptom afflicting the majority of the population at one point or another in their life, it is desired that the general population have at least a rudimentary knowledge of the problem.

Objective: To assess the knowledge of earache amongst the general population of Lahore.

Methodology: It was a Cross Sectional study conducted in Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan from October to November 2020. Consenting individuals of any age and gender were included in our study. The individual had to be a resident of Lahore during the time the research was conducted. Questionnaires of the research topic were provided to individuals that met the inclusion criteria. The questionnaires were distributed both online and some were distributed manually. The data from 256 questionnaires was compiled, statistical data tabulated and finalized. Common trends and patterns were found and written. Data was entered in SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) version (22). Frequency and percentage was calculated for knowledge regarding otalgia

Results: Most (175-68.4%) of the participants knew that diseases of other areas can cause pain in the ear. Similarly, 55.9% were aware that earaches could constitute an emergency. 41% knew that none of the home remedies presented were advisable and 40.2 % correctly identified the use of over the counter pain killers as an appropriate means of temporarily alleviating pain prior to visiting the doctor. 62.5% were aware that earaches can be a major detriment to the quality of life.

Conclusions: Most individuals had good knowledge of otalgia. Knowledge in certain areas, however, such as when a patient of otalgia should go to the doctor or the places from which otalgia can be referred and whether or not otalgia can be a symptom of potentially life-threatening illness was poor.

Key words: earache, general population, Lahore, knowledge. Inconspicuous

Otolgia is defined as ear pain. This simple definition for this common problem however does not do justice to the complexity of the issue and to the nuisance that this pain can be. The pain can range

from a mild inconvenience to debilitating and this is the reason why earache can be an ENT emergency at times. Earaches can be primary with causes originating in the ear and referred pain that is felt in the ear but stemming from some other area as the ear has a rich nerve supply from multiple different nerves which further innervate multiple other structures, pathology of which can be referred to the ear.

Primary otalgia (that which stems from pathology within the ear) can be due to a variety of pathologies, including many of inflammatory, traumatic and neoplastic etiologies. These include pathologies such as otitis media (most common),² otitis externa,³ foreign bodies,⁴ barotrauma,⁵ Ramsay Hunt synd-

1. Syed Ahmed Shahzaem Hussain
2. Syed Ahmed Shahzain Hussain
3. Syed Muzahir Hussain
1. Department of Community Medicine, Allama Iqbal Medical College, Lahore.
2. Post Graduate Resident, Ear, Nose and Throat Department, Shaikh Khalifa Bin Zayed Al-Nahyan Medical & Dental College, Lahore.
3. Ear, Nose and Throat Department, University of Lahore, Lahore.

Correspondence:

Dr. Syed Ahmed Shahzaem Hussain, Department of Community Medicine, Allama Iqbal Medical College, Lahore.

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rome^{6,7} and mastoiditis.⁸

Referred otalgia and the multiple areas from which this pain can be referred from makes localizing the origin of otalgia a particularly intriguing process. Pain can be referred from the neck,^{9,12} throat,⁹ jaw,¹¹ nose and sinuses, teeth¹⁰ and mouth.¹³ Late diagnosis of otalgia of the referred kind can lead to irreversible consequences.¹⁴ Undetected progression of pathology affecting the areas from which pain can be referred from can be very detrimental. Indeed, lethal conditions such as carcinoma of the tongue can cause pain in the ear with dire, possibly fatal results if not promptly managed.

Quality of life among patients with otalgia can be adversely affected with sleep disorders, headaches, fatigue amongst the detriments associated with otalgia. Earaches can affect mental health and may have such an adverse effect that they cause the patient to seek psychiatric help.^{15,16} Otolgia can affect different age groups, children suffering from primary otalgia and adults most often are afflicted with referred otalgia.¹⁴

By gauging the patient's knowledge of earaches, medical professionals can more appropriately mold their approach to counselling the patient regarding their problem, tackling issues which patients might not have adequate knowledge of or which are more pertinent to alleviating the patient's condition and distress. The patient's perception of an illness is one of the key determining factors of how they will comply with the treatment. By assessing the patient's knowledge and understanding which areas need to be classified or explained in more detail, the patient's perception of his own condition may be altered in a positive way which may ultimately aid them into becoming healthy once again. For this reason, we have put together this article in order to give health professionals adequate insight into the extent of patient's knowledge regarding otalgia.

The objective of the study was to assess the knowledge of earache amongst the general population of Lahore.

METHODOLOGY

Questionnaires of the research topic were provided to individuals that met the inclusion criteria. The questionnaires were distributed both online and manually. The data from 256 questionnaires was compiled, statistical data tabulated and finalized. Common trends and patterns were found and written. All the data collected was entered in SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) version (22). The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentage and the quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation. The independent variable was cross tabulated with the dependent variable (x) and any association was found using chi square test of significance. A p value of ≤ 0.05 was taken as statistically significant.

RESULTS

The study was conducted amongst 256 individuals, all of whom were not employed as medical professionals. Of these individuals, 161(62.9%) stated that they have previously experienced an earache whilst 92(35.9%) stated that they had never experienced an earache. 3(1.2%) participants failed to give a response. It was surprising to see that most individuals 141(55.1%) were not aware that it is not advisable to regularly clean the ear with cotton buds/Q tips/ hairpins and 114(44.5%) out of a possible 256 answered correctly with 1(0.4%) individual failing to give any response.

A large number 175(68.4%) of participants knew that diseases of other areas can cause pain in the ear .i.e. referred pain with only 81(31.6%) individuals being unaware of this fact. No individual was able to correctly identify all the locations from which pain can be referred from with none of the individuals able to identify all the correct options. Of the 256 respondents 143(55.9%) knew that earaches can be severe enough to be dealt as an emergency, 113(44.1%) however answered this question incorrectly. Otolgia can cause agonizing pain, however, on inquiring of the maximum intensity of pain that

can result from earaches few 48(18.8%) were aware that the pain can be very severe, 102(39.8%) respondents thought the pain could maximally be severe, 52(20.3%) respondents that it could be moderate at most and 54(21.1%) individuals believed that earache could not be more than mild pain.

105(41.0%) individuals were aware that none of the mentioned home remedies were advisable, 94(36.7%) thought using warm oil was acceptable, 41(16.0%) chose the use of cotton buds to clean the ears whilst 16(6.25%) were under the impression that the use of garlic or garlic juice is beneficial.

Of the respondents, 103(40.2%) were aware that the first aid measure allowing temporary relief of pain before visiting the doctor was the use of over the counter pain medication, 93(36.3%) opted to use oil, 54(21.1%) selected the use of cotton buds and 6(2.3%) chose sponging.

143 (55.9%) were aware that ringing in the ears, hearing loss and loss of balance could all be possible symptoms accompanying earache. 113(44.1%) individuals were unable to give the correct response. 160(62.5%) individuals were aware of this whilst 96(37.5%) individuals failed to give the appropriate response. 11(4.3%) respondents were able to select the correct options. The remaining individuals were not able to identify all of these options. (78(30.5%)) Less than half of the respondents (78-30.5%) knew that earaches could be a symptom of potentially life-

threatening diseases. 27(10.5%) people were aware that uncontrolled diabetes could lead to earaches despite diabetes being a very common disease.

DISCUSSION

In order to effectively deal with any medical issue, the population should have a basic understanding of what the problem is, why they are experiencing it and at the very least rudimentary comprehension of how to deal with the problem in the initial phase (in particular knowing when they should seek the aid of a medical professional). It is ‘knowledge’ of these aspects that we particularly emphasize in our article. There is a great paucity of literature focused on this specific area of interest and in a broader view in any literature focused on gauging knowledge of otalgia, regardless of the population. As such, it is an arduous task to support our findings with data from other studies on this topic as it simply does not exist. However, we were able to find several studies that support the validity, accuracy and relevance of the questions put forward to the study population and so are highlighting them here.

Ear ache is a common condition and frequent cause of visits to primary care physicians.^{17,18} Adegbiyi et al¹⁹ reported prevalence data of 36.2% (i.e. 947 out of 2616), although not strictly prevalence data 62.9% of individuals in our study reported that they have experienced an earache during their lifetime, further highlighting how common this

Table 1:

Variables n=256	Correct response		Incorrect response	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Is it advisable to clean ears regularly with cotton buds/ Q tips/ hairpins?	114	44.5	141	55.1
Can diseases of other areas cause pain in the ear i.e referred pain?	175	31.6	81	68.4
If yes, which areas can the pain be referred from? Pick the correct answer(s)?	0	100.0	256	0.0
Can earaches be severe enough to be dealt as an emergency?	143	44.1	113	55.9
What is the maximum intensity of pain that earaches can cause?	48	81.3	208	18.8
Which home remedies are recommended for earaches?	105	59.0	151	41.0
What first aid measures can be used at home before consulting a doctor in order to achieve temporary relief of pain?	103	59.8	153	40.2
What other symptoms/features can occur with earaches?	143	44.1	113	55.9
How can earaches affect quality of life?	160	37.5	96	62.5
When should you consult a doctor for earache? Select the right option(s)	11	95.7	245	4.3
Can earache be the presenting symptom of life-threatening diseases?	78	69.5	178	30.5
Which of the following diseases can lead to ear ache if not properly treated?	27	89.5	229	10.5

problem really is.

Use of cotton buds to clean the ears can be very detrimental leading to otitis externa and foreign body retention, both important causes of earache.²⁰ It has been repeatedly found that right ear otalgia is more frequent than both left ear otalgia and bilateral otalgia^{21,22,23} which can be easily explained as most of the world's population is right-handed and therefore cleans the right ear more. Furthermore, a study conducted amongst the pediatric population of the US²⁴ showed that 263338 children were treated for cotton tip applicator related injury in ER, which they state is actually an underestimation. This again emphasizes the role of the use of cotton buds as a major cause of otalgia. 55.1% of the individuals in our study were not aware that it is not advisable to clean the ears regularly with cotton tip applicators. Other studies also report finding this misconception in the tested sample.^{25,26,27}

A larger number of individuals (68.4%) were aware that pain can be referred from other parts of the body to the ear. Indeed, in a study of 500 visiting the ENT clinic 58 presented with primary otalgia and 28 with secondary.²⁸ Another research¹⁹ reported that 32.63% of the total cases of otalgia were cases of secondary otalgia. Another study found 12.2% of patients of otalgia had pain referred from other areas. Toothaches and TM joint pathology were reported to be frequent causes of referred otalgia.

Earaches can cause excruciating pain and can present as an emergency. One study focusing on earaches due to swimming in the US estimated that earaches due to swimming alone caused 39900 ER visits. In a study conducted in Nigeria,¹⁹ 34.7% earaches were severe enough to warrant presentation to the ER.

On inquiring of the remedies used prior to presentation to the ENT department, one research¹⁹ found that 49.8% of individuals used over the counter medication, 24.6% used herbal medication, 17.8% used prescribed medication and 7.7% took no treatment. We similarly found that 40.2% respondents in our study were aware that over the counter

pain medication could be used for temporary pain relief prior to presentation to the ENT department.

A multitude of symptoms can accompany otalgia, some common ones being tinnitus, vertigo and hearing loss. The literature is replete with examples of this, with many articles giving a number of symptoms^{14,17,19,20,29,30} associated with otalgia and emphasizing mention of these symptoms during history taking.³¹ 55.9% individuals were able to correctly identify the symptoms that could be associated with earache.

Quality of life can be starkly impacted by earaches. A study conducted in Nigeria¹⁹ showed 65.7% patients reported sleep disturbances, 54.5% missed work, 49.7% decline in social functioning. Another study focusing on otalgia in swimmers noted 24% patients had missed activity with a median of 2 days of activity impacted by earache.²⁴

Earaches can be more than a mere inconvenience and can be a symptom of underlying potentially life-threatening conditions such as carcinoma of different regions.^{19,32,33,34,35} A case was reported in which otalgia was the presenting symptom of nasopharyngeal carcinoma.³⁰ 33% of patients of carcinoma of the base of the tongue had otalgia in one study.¹³ Another study reported that 6% of the cases of referred otalgia were due to pharyngeal carcinoma.³⁶ Metastasis from far of regions can be a cause of earaches, as is exemplified in a study by Dally.³⁷

Diabetes has emerged as a major disease of the masses in the post-industrial era with both lower income countries and more affluent nations being afflicted with the illness and its myriad of complications. Amongst its complications, necrotizing malignant otitis externa is a cause of extreme pain in the ear.³¹ Diabetes is an important point in history taking in a patient with otalgia²⁹ and should always be considered in diabetics with severe ear pain.³¹

CONCLUSION

Overall, the results were promising showing that most individuals had good knowledge of otal-

gia. Knowledge in certain areas, however, such as when a patient of otalgia should go to the doctor or the places from which otalgia can be referred from and whether or not otalgia can be a symptom of potentially life-threatening illness was poor.

Recommendations

The authors suggest the use of published works, televised educational programs and the utilization of mass media platforms such as the internet to promote education of the matters pertaining to the knowledge of earache such as to enhance knowledge and remove possible misconceptions.

Limitations

Our study does admittedly suffer from some limitations. The sample size is relatively small and convenience sampling may slightly influence the results.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare there is no conflict of interests.

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Contributions of the authors

- Conception or design of the work: Dr Syed Ahmed Shahzaem Hussain, Dr Syed Ahmed Shahzain Hussain
- Data collection: Dr Syed Ahmed Shahzaem Hussain, Dr Syed Ahmed Shahzain Hussain, Dr Syed Muzahir Hussain,
- Data analysis and interpretation: Dr Syed Ahmed Shahzaem Hussain
- Drafting the article: Dr Syed Ahmed Shahzaem Hussain
- Critical revision of the article: Dr Syed Muzahir Hussain, Dr Syed Ahmed Shahzaem Hussain
- Final approval of the version to be published: Dr Syed Muzahir Hussain, Dr Syed Ahmed Shahzaem Hussain

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